

An Integrated Life-Course Approach for Person-Centred Solutions and Care for Ageing with Multi-morbidity in the European Regions – STAGE; Stay Healthy Through Ageing

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3	Erasmus University Medical Center	EMC
4	University of Turin	UNITO
5	Utrecht University	UU
6	Stichting VUMC	AUMC
7	Region Hovedstaden	RH
8	University Medical Center Groningen	UMCG
9	University of Barcelona	UB
10	University of Rome Tor Vergata	UTORV
11	Technical University of Munich	TUM
12	University of Liège	UL
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14	Ab.Acus SRL	ABACUS
15	Software Research & Development and Consultancy Corp (SRDC)	SRDC
16	Liva Healthcare A/S	LIVA
17	WeDo Project Intelligence Made Easy SL	WEDO
18	University of Haifa	UH
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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALSPAC	The Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification
ATHLETE	Advancing Tools for Human Early Lifecourse Exposome Research and Translation
BiB	Born in Bradford
BMI	Body Mass Index
BP	Blood Pressure
CIHNR	Copenhagen Infant Health Nurse Records
CKFF	Center for Clinical Research and Prevention; Center for Klinisk Forskning og Forebyggelse
CPC	Copenhagen Perinatal Cohort
CSHRR	Copenhagen School Health Records Register
DAA	Data Access Agreement

DanFunD	The Danish study of Functional Disorders
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCAT-AP	DCAT Application Profile
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
DUO	Data Use Ontology
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ECCN	EU Child Cohort Network
EHEN	European Human Exposome Network
EXPANSE	the EXposome Powered tools for healthy living in urbAN SETtings project
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GECCO	The Geoscience and Health Cohort Consortium
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
H2020	Horizon 2020
HL7	Health Level 7
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
IHEN	International Human Exposome Network
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KORA	Cooperative Health Research in the Region of Augsburg
LS AAI	Life Science Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure
M	Million
MB	Megabyte
MIABIS	Minimum Information About Biobank Data Sharing
MTA	Material Transfer Agreement
NFBC	Northern Finland Birth Cohorts
NHAI	Neighbourhood Healthy Ageing Index
NINFEA	Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente
PI	Principal Investigator
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
UK	United Kingdom
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

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INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the STAGE Data Management Plan (DMP) is to outline data policy and data management in this large-scale, international project. This document provides an overview of:

- how data is handled and managed within the project;
- what data will be re-used in the project;
- what data will be collected and used;
- what methodologies and standards will be applied;
- how data are and will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR); and
- how and where data is stored.

STAGE aims to access, inter-operationalise, re-use and further FAIRify European health data and a catalogue of life-course cohorts, administrative health data and biobanks for life-course health research. With one of the largest collections of life-course exposome and genome-wide data and further links to medical and health data, STAGE aims to study, predict and prevent the risk of ageing with multi-morbidity and support opportunities staying healthy and active throughout the life-course.

The STAGE DMP mainly addresses the use and handling of existing research data, later listed in Table 1, but also describes the outlines of data collections during the project. All these research data contain sensitive personal data, and the data controllers have their own ethical statements and data security measures in place. Therefore, it is not possible to give very detailed descriptions of the management of every dataset. In general, the STAGE project management is not involved in the data management of the research data controlled by other data controllers. The data management is a duty of each data controller of each separate dataset.

The data collections in the KORA and NFBC1966 studies are considered in this DMP. Other data collections that will be performed during the STAGE project are in the planning phase and only preliminary protocols are in place, these data collections will be considered only briefly in this document and described in more detail in the updates of this DMP. The collection, handling and making the data FAIR, is the responsibility of each data controller. In general, the STAGE project management is not involved in data management of the research data collected in the project; data management will be a duty of the data controller of each dataset.

DATA SUMMARY

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

In its research, the STAGE project will almost exclusively be re-using data and enriching the unique repertoire of the harmonised EU Child Cohort Network which was first established in the LifeCycle project (EU Horizon 2020 programme, grant agreement No 733206) and which is now being further expanded as part of the Horizon 2020 projects LongITools (grant agreement No 874739), EUCAN-Connect (grant agreement No 824989), ATHLETE (grant agreement No 874583) and some other European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects. As a result, the European Health Research Data and Sample Catalogue, later “the Data Catalogue”, has been developed by the Molgenis team in Groningen (partner UMCG), the Netherlands. This is a FAIR data catalogue of high (multi-)dimensional and complementary data across the life course, including prospective birth cohorts, longitudinal studies in adults, register-based cohorts, randomised controlled trials and biobanks.

Throughout its implementation, unless specified otherwise, STAGE will access, inter-operationalise, re-use (Work Packages (WP) 3–7) and further FAIRify (WP9) a catalogue of life-course cohorts, administrative health data and biobanks as described in Figure 1. It represents one of the largest collections of data with genome-wide, life-course exposome, epigenetics, metabolomics and proteomics data and further links to medical and health data with the aim of developing and actioning models to study, predict and prevent different types of ageing with multi-morbidity throughout the life-course.

During the STAGE project, the consortium expects to re-use existing data from the datasets listed in Table 1. These are the datasets recognised by the consortium members at the start of the project, and the list is expected to expand during the six years of the STAGE project. The data will be used for research activities according to each data controller’s conditions. As part of the STAGE project, new data will be collected in the KORA and NFBC1966 cohort studies.

Table 1. List of datasets in STAGE

Name of the dataset	Full name of the dataset
AIRWAVE	The Airwave Tissue Bank
ALSPAC G0	The Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (Parents)
ALSPAC G1	The Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (Children)
BiB G0	Born in Bradford (Women)
BiB G1	Born in Bradford (Children)
CIHNR	Copenhagen Infant Health Nurse Records
CPC	Copenhagen Perinatal Cohort
CSHRR	Copenhagen School Health Records Register
DanFunD	The Danish study of Functional Disorders
DanFunDxC SHRR	Copenhagen School Health Records Register x The Danish study of Functional Disorders overlap

Generation R G0	Generation R (parents)
Generation R G1	Generation R (children)
Generation R Next G0	Generation R Next (parents)
Generation R Next G1	Generation R Next (children)
KORA	Cooperative Health Research in the Region of Augsburg
NFBC1966	Northern Finland Birth Cohort 1966
NFBC1986	Northern Finland Birth Cohort 1986
NINFEA G0	Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente (Mothers)
NINFEA G1	Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente (Children)
GECCO	The Geoscience and Health Cohort Consortium
FinnGen	The FinnGen study
Health Search	Health Search, a research-oriented database of Electronic Clinical Records from the Italian Society of General Practitioners and Primary Care Doctors (SIMG)
UK Biobank	United Kingdom Biobank

Figure 1. Summary of STAGE life-course cohorts, administrative data and biobanks
 ICD: international classification of diseases, BMI: body mass index; BP blood pressure, ATC: Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical

What types and formats of data will the project re-use?

The data listed in Table 1 which the consortium is considering re-using, consist of various formats used for raw data storage, depending on the data controller's procedures and structure of the data. The epigenetic (DNA methylation), genetic, metabolomics, proteomics, and imaging data are stored using various standard file formats for each specific data type.

Figure 1 describes the types of data available in the longitudinal cohorts, administrative health data and biobanks available to the STAGE researchers. Different data types in the figure include genome (G); social, lifestyle and environmental exposures (E); diagnostics, e.g. International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes (D); clinical, e.g. body mass index, blood pressure (C); self-reports (SR); medications, e.g. Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification (M); and proteome, metabolome and methylome (omics). Length of follow-up is denoted by arrows in the figure.

Genetic data are available in AIRWAVE, ALSPAC, BiB, CSHRR, DanFund, DanFundxCSHRR, Generation R, KORA, NFBC, GECCO, FinnGen, and UK Biobank. Social, lifestyle and environmental exposures are available in all longitudinal cohorts and in the UK Biobank. FinnGen and Health Search datasets do not have social, lifestyle or environmental exposure data. Proteome, metabolome, or methylome data, or all three, have been collected in AIRWAVE, ALSPAC, BiB G0, Generation R G1, Generation R Next G1, KORA, NFBC, NINFEA, GECCO, and UK Biobank.

Length of follow-up varies between cohorts and biobanks, with follow-up ages ranging from preconception to one hundred years old. All datasets have at least some medical data available. Diagnostic data are available in AIRWAVE, CIHNR, CPC, CSHRR, DanFund, DanFundxCSHRR, KORA, NFBC, GECCO, FinnGen, Health Search, and UK Biobank. Clinical data are available in all cohorts and biobanks, except for NINFEA, and FinnGen. Self-reported medical information data are available in all cohorts, except for CIHNR, CPC, and CSHRR. UK Biobank has self-reports available, but FinnGen, and Health Search do not. Data on medications are available for all cohorts and biobanks, except for ALSPAC, BiB, NINFEA, and FinnGen.

What types and formats of data will the project generate?

During the STAGE project, data will be collected in the NFBC1966 and KORA studies in WP8. We will invite the participants of the NFBC1966 and the KORA (Figure 1) studies to participate in an examination to assess their current state of health and prevalence of multi-morbidity starting in 2026. Subsequently, the health monitoring and intervention study will build upon information collected over the life-course.

Within the NFBC1966 study, we will pilot the use of health monitoring system to detect multi-morbidity with partner ABACUS in WP7 the ultimate aim being to increase cost effectiveness of health care. All data will be analysed for adherence to the study protocols, outcomes, effectiveness, and healthcare costs.

Within the KORA study, we will implement a personalised health programme involving coaches and health monitoring. Specifically, together with partner LIVA in WP7 we will pilot a person-centred coaching programme optimised to address risk factors of multi-morbidity. To this end, we will use the methodology of established and effective prevention programmes for serving person-centred prevention of multi-morbidity.

It should be noted that the data collected during the STAGE project in the KORA and NFBC1966 studies will be most likely fully utilised only after the project has ended. The data collection is set to take place between months 24–54 (2026 January to 2028 June) of the STAGE project. Due to the substantial amount of time and effort it will take to process these data, the collected data will be fully available for research use only after the project has ended in December 2029. Metadata about the new data not previously registered in the Data Catalogue will be added to the Data Catalogue as part of the STAGE project.

Within WP6, co-creation methodology will be used to develop functional, clinical, ethical and legal requirements for AI tools. Co-creation activities engage stakeholders and information (data) is collected from stakeholders with electronic surveys and interviews. WP6, WP7 and WP8 activities all tie together with the aim of creating an ethical and trustworthy AI-tool for predicting multi-morbidity trajectories and tools to monitor health and interventions, support decision making in healthcare and deliver personalised interventions.

WP3 will deliver an evidence-informed neighbourhood healthy ageing index (NHAi) in which high-resolution geographic information systems (GIS) data with cross-EU coverage, combined to local data at the pilot study areas will be used. Based on environmental exposure data, we will develop two prototypes of the NHAi (one Europe-wide, and one with more refined components in local areas where pilot studies take place), leading to an interactive healthy-ageing web-based atlas. We will also invite seniors and close caregivers to iteratively assess and enhance the NHAi, nurturing it with their territorial intelligence. Healthy Ageing Observatories will eventually be implemented in each regional pilot-study area (Germany and Finland) to empower local participants in proactively uploading data of their place-based perceptions and ensure the web-based atlas' update beyond the STAGE project duration.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

STAGE aims to demonstrate the importance and feasibility of a life-course approach to prevent accelerated ageing, as defined by the accumulation of multi-morbidity, and to integrate knowledge into transferable person-centred solutions for early diagnosis and screening, treatment, and long-term management of multi-morbidity. To achieve this, STAGE is proposing a life-course approach to better understand ageing with multi-morbidity, providing evidence-based solutions to support the transformation of healthcare to address the profound health and demographic challenges ahead. The approach capitalises on European collaborations of longitudinal cohorts and biobanks spanning the entire life course,

actioning exposome and disease networks trajectory analysis, as well as, the biology of ageing, to explore how a person develops ageing with multi-morbidity.

The project objectives integrate an ethical, social, historical, and infrastructural framework; environmental, epidemiological, and biological life-course approaches; artificial intelligence (AI) powered integrated person-centred solutions and applications; cohort-based clinical studies; and a FAIR life-course health and geospatial data portal with robust management, dissemination, engagement and exploitation activities.

STAGE project's evidence-based methods will translate into a person-centred prevention in longitudinal cohorts in Finland and Germany, co-designed with citizens, patients, healthcare providers, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and policymakers. It will also embed social sciences and humanities and engage stakeholders to develop a NHA, person-centred predictions of multi-morbidity, and healthcare and policy recommendations. Ultimately, STAGE will create solutions for agile, high-quality, person-centred health and care services that are life-course and gender sensitive, needs-based, and designed to enhance resilience and participation.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

In STAGE there are twenty cohorts, two biobanks and one administrative health database involved, with a total of 3,873,757 study participants across the data sources. With genetic, proteome, metabolome, and methylome data, in addition to social, lifestyle and environmental exposures collected across the cohorts and registers, with long follow-ups and multiple data collections for most participants, it is impossible to estimate the exact amount of data that will be re-used during STAGE. The estimated size of the metadata that is deposited in the Data Catalogue will be under 100MB.

Data will be generated during the STAGE project in the KORA and NFBC1966 studies. Expected number of observations (individuals) in these data collections is estimated to be about 4,000 in KORA and about 7,000 in NFBC1966.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The information regarding origin and provenance of the re-used data from cohorts can be found in the dataset cards in Annex 1. The origins of the three sources of administrative health data, electronic clinical records and biobanks are Finland (FinnGen), Italy (Health Search), and United Kingdom (UK Biobank). Metadata in the Data Catalogue originates from the individual cohorts, registries, etc. where the data is stored.

The origin of generated data during STAGE in KORA will be Germany, and the origin of generated data in NFBC1966 will be Finland.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data collected and used in the STAGE project should be useful e.g. to health researchers, health practitioners, policymakers and EU citizens (via e.g. the AI-tool developed in WP6). The data and the tools developed during STAGE, are made FAIR for constant, cost efficient and rapid scientific renewal in Europe, and for policy making.

FAIR DATA

MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

All the data, either re-used or generated in STAGE are personal health data. All data are subject to the relevant national and EU laws and regulations regarding data protection and security. For these reasons none of the datasets involved in STAGE will be openly available, nor will they be identified by a persistent identifier.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Metadata are available for all data that are listed in Table 1, links to metadata can be found in Annex 1 and 2. New metadata will be generated in the KORA and NFBC1966 studies, with the data collections taking place during STAGE. The datasets that will harmonise their variables during the project, according to harmonisation protocols, will also create new metadata which will be available in the Data Catalogue. All datasets involved in STAGE are anticipated to join the Data Catalogue, so that all applicable metadata will be openly available. All datasets included in STAGE follow standard epidemiological terminology in their metadata.

WP9 will deliver a life-course and spatial data intelligence portal to streamline internal and external reuse of STAGE data and non-data assets, i.e. individual-level data, geographical data, reference data, methods, models and tools.

The STAGE life-course and spatial data intelligence portal will integrate previously parallel efforts with the products of STAGE partners into a unified data and tool landscape based on the FAIR principles. We will first integrate and further develop the Data Catalogue that describes the available rich individual-level data from EU cohort studies, such as those collected by the EU Child Cohort Network (ECCN) and the EHEN, using the long-standing MOLGENIS catalogue platform, which also incorporates established FAIR standards such as the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT). We will combine these with FAIR representations of geospatial modelling and spatially resolved maps developed in the EXposome Powered

tools for healthy living in urBAN SETtings (EXPANSE) project. Finally, we will operate and support integrated access to all these FAIRified resources, including a visual user experience with single sign-on based on Life Science Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure, LS AAI (previously ELIXIR AAI, <https://lifescienceri.eu/>).

The platform will then integrate: (i) a user interface to support other (non-STAGE) datasets to join the Data Catalogue, (ii) a policy simulation intelligence, inspired by WP3 to support policies for healthy-ageing neighbourhoods and (iii) integrated portal user experience and support.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use? Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Search on metadata is possible in the Data Catalogue (WP9) and all related metadata will be openly accessible through the Data Catalogue at <https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/>.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Data to be re-used in STAGE is stored according to standards appropriate to each data controller. Each data controller, and their chosen trusted repositories, ensures the long-term preservation and curation of their data, according to national and EU laws and regulations.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

All data controllers have arrangements with trusted repositories that comply with national and EU laws and regulations regarding data protection and security. More information on each dataset can be found in their respective dataset card in Annex 1, and in Annex 2 for administrative health data and biobanks.

For the data generated during the STAGE project in the NFBC1966 and KORA studies, appropriate arrangements are in place and the data will be placed in the repositories already in operation with the cohorts.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Metadata in the Data Catalogue is stored using DCAT and the Minimum Information About Biobank Data Sharing (MIABIS) initiative.

All the data in the STAGE project are personal health data. All data are subject to the relevant national and EU laws and regulations regarding data protection and security. For these reasons none of the datasets involved in STAGE have been assigned an identifier to a digital object, nor will the repository, chosen by each data controller, assign an identifier.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

All the data, either re-used or generated, in STAGE are personal health data. All data are subject to the relevant national and EU laws and regulations regarding data protection and security. For these reasons none of the datasets involved in STAGE will be openly available.

The Data Catalogue will document the access conditions for each dataset, and the Data Catalogue itself is openly available for public access. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2, for information about possible restrictions on data sharing for each dataset.

Table 2. Data accessibility: Data

Name of the dataset	Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?
AIRWAVE	No
ALSPAC G0	No (free for consortium-projects)
ALSPAC G1	No (free for consortium-projects)
BiB G0	No
BiB G1	No
CIHNR	Yes
CPC	Yes
CSHRR	Yes
DanFunD	No
DanFunDxCSHRR	No
Generation R	No (free for consortium-projects)
Generation R G1	No (free for consortium-projects)
Generation R Next G0	No (free for consortium-projects)
Generation R Next G1	No (free for consortium-projects)
KORA	Yes
NFBC1966	No
NFBC1986	No
NINFEA G0	Yes
NINFEA G1	Yes
GECCO	Yes

FinnGen	No (free for FinnGen partner organisations)
Health Search	No
UK Biobank	No

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Currently, at the start of the project, there is no anticipated intellectual property to which an embargo should be applied to.

The data collected during the STAGE project within the KORA and NFBC1966 studies will be most likely fully utilised in later projects. The data collection is set to take place between months 24–54 (January 2026 to June 2028) of the STAGE project. Due to the substantial amount of time and effort it takes to process these data, the collected data might be fully available for research use only after the project has ended in December 2029. When the research data are ready for use, they will be available through the access protocols described in the dataset cards of the KORA and NFBC studies in Annex 1.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?

See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for information on access protocols for each dataset. To access the metadata, only the URL of the Data Catalogue is required: <https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/>.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for information on how access will be provided to the data and how the identity of a person accessing the data will be ascertained.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee in STAGE at the project level. Each data controller has a data access committee already in place and operational. All requests to access data must be directed to the data controllers. All requests need to go through an access protocol the data controller has described. Descriptions of data access protocols can be found in the dataset cards in Annex 1.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Data controllers store their own metadata according to their respective protocols. Data controllers may have different national, regional or departmental laws and regulations regarding access conditions for metadata related to sensitive data, omics data, and metadata that is not deposited into the Data Catalogue. The data controllers will provide more information about data and metadata on request and access protocols for each dataset are described in the dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2.

Metadata deposited in the Data Catalogue will be openly accessible at <https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/>. Within the Data Catalogue, datasets also have the opportunity to store information regarding their individual data access procedures for all interested parties to view. Metadata about harmonised variables will be deposited in the Data Catalogue.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Metadata deposited in the Data Catalogue will remain available and findable permanently, or as long as it remains funded. After the end of STAGE, and other Horizon Europe projects which fund the Data Catalogue, there will be a need for external funding to maintain the Data Catalogue indefinitely.

All metadata are also stored by the data controllers, especially metadata not deposited in the Data Catalogue. All data are also stored by the data controllers. These metadata and data will remain available and findable according to each data controller's regulations. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?

Currently, at the start of the project, none of the datasets involved in the STAGE project have software included in the metadata. Data will be accessible and readable with open-source software. If needed, documentation of any necessary software for data usage will be included in the metadata.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Implementation of the Data Catalogue is based on standards developed in EUCAN-connect, plus The DCAT Application Profile (DCAT-AP) v3 (plus Health Extension when it becomes available) and FAIR data points (FDP)¹.

In WP7, Health Level 7 (HL7) Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard will be used to enable interoperability of the data exchange among WP7 components. We also plan to model the data collected in WP8 in HL7 FHIR to make it easily re-usable afterwards, and to demonstrate that it can be utilised by the tools to be developed in WP7.

Currently, at the start of the STAGE project, each dataset involved in STAGE uses standard epidemiological terminology in their metadata, which helps interoperability within the project.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Currently most of the categorical information in the Data Catalogue uses well-established ontologies such as the Data Use Ontology (DUO), ICD-10, etc. Currently, at the start of the STAGE project, none of the datasets involved in STAGE use uncommon or project specific ontologies or vocabularies. If at some point in the project, usage of uncommon ontologies or vocabularies becomes unavoidable, mappings to more common ones will be provided.

Will your data include qualified references² to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

The STAGE project will almost exclusively re-use and reference to existing data on datasets referenced in this data management plan and listed in Table 1. There will be efforts to harmonise data across datasets involved in STAGE and harmonised data reference each other. In the Data Catalogue anyone will be able to see per variable how each dataset has harmonised to that variable (syntax, variable(s) involved).

¹ Swertz, Gini et al "Towards an Interoperable Ecosystem of Research Cohort and Real-world Data Catalogues Enabling Multi-center Studies" <https://www.thieme-connect.de/products/ejournals/abstract/10.1055/s-0042-1742522>

² A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

INCREASE DATA RE-USE

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Within the Data Catalogue each dataset listed in Table 1 will have the opportunity to provide codebooks and information on how each variable has been harmonised to the STAGE variables. Metadata and other documentation are also available via the data controllers. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The majority of the data used in STAGE, either re-used or generated, are personal health data and, therefore, cannot be made freely available. All personal data are subject to the relevant national and EU laws and regulations regarding data protection and security. However, all applicable metadata will be openly accessible through the Data Catalogue at <https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/>.

Regarding the data collected in the WP3, WP6 and WP7, plans have been made regarding what data can be made freely available and how this will be done. The STAGE consortium will list at the end of the project in the updated version of this DMP (D1.5):

- What kind of data was generated during the project lifetime, and
- How, where and when the generated data will be available.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Data generated during the project in WP8 can be accessed by third parties via data access protocols set by the data controllers. For better descriptions, see the dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2. Later in the project, this information is anticipated to be available also in the Data Catalogue. Regarding the data collected in the WP3, WP6 and WP7, initial plans have been made and this information will be updated in the Deliverable 1.5 *Data Management Plan – Update*.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The provenance of the data will be documented by the data controllers and the Data Catalogue. Metadata deposited in the Data Catalogue will also contain information about the methods used in the harmonisation of each dataset's variables. See the dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

For each dataset involved in the STAGE project, each data controller is responsible for quality assurance processes regarding data and metadata, and possible collection of data and metadata. See the dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

STAGE research outputs will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. STAGE project will also disseminate research outputs through multiple sources e.g. on:

- STAGE website: <https://stage-healthyageing.eu/>;
- Social media:
 - LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/the-stage-project/>;
 - X: <https://twitter.com/STAGEPROJECTEU>;
- Newsletters;
- Open co-creation events (in-person and online).

The anticipated Key Exploitable Results (KER) in the STAGE project are described in Table 3. The KERs will be disseminated via channels mentioned above and in various events and meetings arranged with users and other beneficiaries listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Other research outputs in STAGE

Key Exploitable Result	WP	Description	Users and beneficiaries
#1 Recommendations for a life-course approach to ageing, age-friendly societies, with generic definitions and narrative of the types of ageing with multi-morbidity.	2 to 10	Evidence-based recommendations and policies, co-developed to gain expert consensus, to maintain a person's functional ability and reduce the risks of ageing with multi-morbidity. The recommendations will be tested in a relevant context during the project.	Policymakers including WHO and EU Parliament, healthcare community, regional and national planning authorities, medical schools, patient and advocacy groups, citizens
#2 Age-Friendly Neighbourhood Atlas, containing	3 & 9	Europe-wide digital, interactive healthy ageing atlas providing an evidence informed neighbourhood	Policymakers (public health and planning), citizens, researchers

<p>neighbourhood characteristics related to healthy and active ageing</p>		<p>healthy aging index of all regions of Europe. It will provide policy intelligence and made accessible as part of KER#6.</p>	
<p>#3 FAIR and Actionable Scientific Outputs: Protocols for harmonised definitions for the types of ageing with multi-morbidity, open-source methods for epigenetic, metabolomic and proteomic hallmarks of ageing as intermediate outcomes in trials. Causal models and instruments, econometric microsimulation.</p>	<p>4 & 5</p>	<p>Transferable scientific knowledge advancing our understanding of ageing, its determinants and the biological mechanisms involved. Published as preprint / articles in gold open access journals with publicly available summary statistics. Protocols, open access tools using harmonised European-wide data (EHEN catalogues) and ICD codes, accessible through KER#6 and supported by capacity building activities in KER#8.</p>	<p>Researchers, including those undertaking trials and those aiming to understand the biological processes underlying ageing, healthcare communities, including practitioners, pharmaceutical companies, other funded projects in the same Horizon Europe Destination.</p>
<p>#4 Trustworthy and Robust Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools</p>	<p>6 & 7</p>	<p>AI tools to support healthy ageing by predicting the risks (via a devoted AI model) of the different types of ageing with multi-morbidity throughout the life-course.</p>	<p>Citizens, researchers, policymakers, healthcare community, digital healthcare product developers (SMEs)</p>
<p>#5 Integrative Digital Platform for Person-centred Solutions and Care</p>	<p>7 & 8</p>	<p>Digital platform screening for the types of ageing with multi-morbidity via a predictive risk-based tool (KER#4), fed by clinical (KER#2 and 3) and lifestyle (coming from daily monitoring) data driving a personalised health coaching app. The effectiveness of the solutions for passive monitoring and active interventions will be directly tested in two life-course population-based cohorts (WP8). All protocols are registered with data transferred to KER#6.</p>	<p>Citizens (healthy and those with multi-morbidity) aged 50+, primary healthcare, SMEs developing new healthcare products, policymakers, economists, clinicians, researchers</p>

#6 FAIR Life-course and Spatial Data and Policy Intelligence Portal	3, 4 & 9	A FAIR trusted environment, with federated accessibility to life-course cohorts and a resource for geospatial information. A library of mathematical models for transparent and interpretable analysis of the data. A FAIR data point for external users and a policy intelligence tool to plan interventions and future policies.	Researchers, users of data to develop policies or healthcare interventions, policymakers, users of big data, other funded projects in the same Horizon Europe Destination.
#7 Healthy Ageing Lab	2 to 10	Public facing web-based platform and community of stakeholders, hosting resources and educational materials and tools: e.g. videos, blogs, healthcare and policy guidelines	All stakeholders but content will be adapted to citizens / policymakers / healthcare community
#8 Healthy Ageing Academy	2 to 10	Web based repository for capacity building and training provider containing scientific publications, visualisation and AI tools, research methods e.g. Delphi studies	Academia / researchers, trainee healthcare professionals

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

WP10 leads the dissemination activities of research results and other publicly available project outcomes. (Detailed plan for the dissemination activities has been made and are listed in D10.1 *PDCE Document to guide the project communication, dissemination and exploitation* (v1); not publicly available). See “Other issues” section for more information about data management related to dissemination activities.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

WP9 and partner UMCG lead the efforts of making data FAIR in STAGE. Person-months allocated for making data FAIR are listed in Table 4. For the Data Catalogue (WP9), the costs pertain to developing a metadata standard, hosting the data, and further development of the interface to access the data.

Table 4. Allocated person-months for data collections and making data FAIR

Beneficiary	WP	Person-months
UMCG	9	72
UOULU	8	64
HMGU	8	29
LIVA	8	41
ABACUS	8	12
SRDC	8	6

In WP8, roughly €3.5M of the STAGE project grant is allocated to the data collections in the KORA and NFBC1966 studies. Roughly €1.5M for the KORA and roughly €2M for NFBC1966 data collection. Staff effort allocated in WP8, related to the data collections, are listed in Table 4.

Data controllers' efforts are largely independent of STAGE, and we anticipate in-kind contributions from the data controllers when on making the data FAIR as the FAIRification of the data will be beneficial also to the data controllers.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Costs for making data and other research outputs FAIR will be covered by the STAGE Horizon Europe grant. Additionally, costs for the Data Catalogue will also be covered by other Horizon Europe grants, including e.g., the International Human Exposome Network (IHEN). We anticipate in-kind contributions from data controllers and researchers in efforts of making their data and research outputs FAIR.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The data management in the STAGE project will be performed by each data controller in their own environments and with their own procedures as required by the national and international laws as well as institutional requirements. The STAGE project management team will help and guide project partners with any issues related to data. All data access requests must go through each data controller's procedures. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information about each dataset.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

The Data Catalogue, and WP9, will ensure metadata preservation. The data controllers are responsible for ensuring the preservation of their own data and related metadata, especially

those metadata not yet in the Data Catalogue. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

The sustainability of long-term preservation of data and metadata in the Data Catalogue are largely dependent on external funding. After the end of current Horizon Europe projects, further external funding is needed to ensure data and metadata preservation. The Data Catalogue can only ensure metadata preservation while it remains funded.

DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data collections and storage are the responsibility of each data controller. Most datasets used in STAGE are well-known and established datasets, which each have their own ethical statements and data security measures in place. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

All data collected within the scope of STAGE activities, are the responsibility of the respective data controller. Protocols for data collection and processing are currently under development. These are especially related to WP3, WP6, WP7 and WP8 activities. Regarding the Data Catalogue security, only open-access metadata is contained, and data submissions are protected using LS AAI.

Some of the data analysis in STAGE will be conducted via the DataSHIELD interface. DataSHIELD is a software solution which allows researchers to conduct federated analysis on datasets (i) without the data being transferred, and (ii) without having access to participant level data. Instead, all cohorts store their data on local servers protected by a firewall. Researchers granted permission to analyse the data log into these servers via an R interface but are not able to view individual data due to a series of disclosure controls. Instead, researchers send analysis commands which are processed separately on each server, and summary data is then returned to the researcher and pooled between cohorts. Thus, researchers can conduct sophisticated analyses without having direct access to the data. More information about DataSHIELD can be found at: <https://www.datashield.ac.uk>.

Despite not involving the transfer of data, all analysis using DataSHIELD is subject to broader governance and ethical principles. All partners are compliant to the Declaration of Helsinki for human research by having informed the volunteers participating in these studies and having obtained informed consent according to procedures approved upfront by competent national ethical authorities. All ethical commitments have been satisfied, including but not limited to: (i) issues related to research involving children/minors, (ii) measures to avoid coercion on participants, (iii) measures to ensure welfare, (iv) justification of involvement of children; (v) issues related to secondary use of data.

In addition, in order to access data via DataSHIELD all researchers will first have to complete Data Access Agreements (DAAs) for all partners/cohorts/studies for which they want to

access the data. The terms of each DAA are drawn up by the governing institution and meets all legal and ethical requirements at a national and international level.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The data to be re-used in STAGE and generated in the NFBC1966 and KORA studies are and will be stored according to standards appropriate to each data controller. Each data controller, and their chosen trusted repositories, ensures the long-term preservation and curation of the data, according to national and EU laws and regulations. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

ETHICS

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Most of the data used and re-used in the STAGE project contain sensitive data of human subjects. Therefore, this data cannot be made fully available, but metadata is and will be available. Members of the STAGE consortium, as do any other researchers wanting use specific datasets, must follow the standard procedures set by each data controller, if they wish to use any datasets other than controlled by themselves. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on the access protocols for each dataset.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Data collection and storage are the responsibility of each data controller. Most datasets used in STAGE are well-known and established datasets, which each have their own ethical statements and data security measures in place. In WP8 new data will be collected in the NFBC1966 and KORA studies and informed consent will be obtained from the participants. In case any other data are collected as part of STAGE activities, proper informed consent will be obtained from the participants and stakeholders, when necessary.

Informed consent has been obtained accordingly for all study participants, except for those in CIHNR, CPC and CSHRR, for which informed consent is not required. The CIHNR and CSHRR cohorts were formed from pre-existing records, thus there were no recruitment, inclusion or exclusion criteria and individuals were never individually contacted. Per Danish regulations on the ethical handling of scientific health research, informed consent procedures do not apply to these cohorts. According to Danish regulations, the CIHNR and CSHRR do not require approval by the scientific ethical committee system (see §14, part 2 in the Danish law on the ethical handling of scientific health research). Use of these data is permitted by the Danish Data Protection Agency under permission P-2019-832.

The CPC cohort was formed by recruiting pregnant women who were admitted to the Copenhagen University Hospital from September 21, 1959, to December 20, 1961. No inclusion or exclusion criteria were applied. At the time of data collection almost 60 years ago, no rules of formal consent were applicable. However, the mothers were all given explanations of the investigation, guaranteed confidentiality, and were given the opportunity not to participate. Additionally, it was voluntary to participate in the follow-ups. According to Danish regulations, the CPC does not require approval by the scientific ethical committee system (see §14, part 2 in the Danish law on the ethical handling of scientific health research). Use of these data is permitted by the Danish Data Protection Agency under permission P-2019-832.

OTHER ISSUES

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Each data controller will be using their own procedures for data management, which follow the necessary national and EU laws and regulations as well as institutional regulations. See dataset cards in Annex 1 and 2 for more information on each dataset.

The STAGE project uses EU procedure for data management plan for the STAGE consortium. This document is constructed according to the Horizon Europe Data management plan template, version 1.1 (01.04.2022). (EU Grants: Data management plan (HE): V1.1 – 01.04.2022).

PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

In general, when any personal data are collected as part of STAGE activities, proper informed consent will be obtained from participants or stakeholders, when necessary. Any personal data collected within the scope of STAGE activities, are the responsibility of the respective data controller. None of the personal data will be shared unless separately agreed between the applying instance and the specific data controller. All personal data collected during the project will only be kept for as long as it is necessary to achieve the goals of the project, or the specific study.

The data collected from the KORA and NFBC1966 study participants, will be stored as part of the given research data collection and used in future research. Documents that are subjected to longer retention periods, e.g. financial documents, will be kept for as long as required by law. If not otherwise specified or required, all personal data collected during the project, shall be destroyed no later than five years after the project has ended.

KORA and NFBC1966

The data collected in the KORA and NFBC1966 studies within WP8 will be considered personal data. The data collection and controlling are the responsibility of respective data controllers. The data collected can contain e.g. the following type of information:

- Contact information,
- Health survey and interview answers,
- Health measurements,
- Biological samples and measurements.

Informed consent will be obtained from all study participants. The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies to the KORA study and NFBC1966. The data collected from the KORA and NFBC1966 study participants, will be stored as part of the given research data collection and used in future research.

STAGE Stakeholder Register

A STAGE Stakeholder Register will be created to collect the information for individuals/organisations within all stakeholder groups. It will include columns for the characterisation details and stakeholder analysis outcomes. The master version will be stored securely by partner WEDO and will be compliant with applicable data protection legislation.

Named individuals will only be contacted by project partners if they are legally able to do so or if the individuals have specifically self-registered for participation, and all personal data will be processed in line with applicable data protection legislation(s). Any necessary data protection forms, privacy notices, and agreements will therefore be developed as required.

STAGE website is used to collect information of people who have left a project enquiry via an electronic form, are interested in subscribing to the STAGE newsletter or will participate in STAGE events. The data controller of these data is partner WEDO. The privacy notice regarding handling of the personal data in STAGE is publicly available on the STAGE website: <https://stage-healthyageing.eu/privacy-policy>.

Personal data of STAGE consortium members and stakeholders

Processing of personal data in the STAGE project can be justified by the legitimate interest of the controller / joint controllers. In STAGE, we will collect as little personal data of the consortium members as possible, and it will be used only to implement the project.

Personal data is collected from the STAGE consortium members, cluster project(s) members (e.g. COMFORTage) and stakeholders, and it includes a maximum of the following information (of which most is publicly available e.g. on institutions and personal websites):

- Name,
- Affiliation information / Company name,

- Academic degrees,
- Area of Expertise,
- Email addresses,
- Phone numbers,
- Meeting documents,
- Reports and deliverables.

Personal data of the consortium members, cluster project(s) members and stakeholders are available in STAGE SharePoint workspace only to STAGE consortium members if they have registered to the SharePoint workspace. The data controller is UOULU.

None of the personal information will be shared outside the consortium unless otherwise agreed with the person(s) in question. Documents that might contain personal information and are subjected to longer retention periods, e.g. financial documents, will be kept for as long as required by law. Otherwise, personal data of the consortium members collected during the project will only be kept for as long as is necessary but will be destroyed no later than five years after the project has ended.

CONCLUSION

This document is the first version of the STAGE project's DMP and describes using, collecting and storing of the different types of data in general. In this large-scale project re-using data of more than 3.8 M European citizens and collecting new data in several European countries, many different national laws and regulations, and institutional regulations apply. Therefore, not all data management procedures and applicable laws and regulations can be listed in one document. However, we have collected 'dataset cards' (Annex 1 and 2) of all the possible datasets of which we anticipate using data in this project. The dataset cards provide information specific to each listed dataset including e.g., who is the data controller, where the data is located and how to gain access to the data. More specific information regarding e.g. ethical documents and data management is available upon request from each respective data controller. The STAGE DMP will be updated throughout the project, when necessary (updates available upon request), and at the end of the project as another public Deliverable D1.5 (M65).

ANNEX 1 – DATASET CARDS

Table A1. STAGE dataset card - AIRWAVE

Name of the data	The Airwave Tissue Bank
Date of information	17-06-2024
Study design	Longitudinal cohort study
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Britain, United Kingdom
STAGE partner contact	Imperial College London, Marc Chadeau-Hyam
Website	https://police-health.org.uk/
Link to metadata	https://police-health.org.uk/data-dictionary-version-2
How to apply for data (link)	https://police-health.org.uk/applying-access-resource
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Imperial College London
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	AIRWAVE data are stored indefinitely (no end date defined).
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) is needed with co-operational organisations needing access to the data. DTA is done once the material request is accepted by the AIRWAVE committee. Access will be arranged through the server at Imperial College London.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Ascertained through the data access process.
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The AIRWAVE datasets are not publicly available. Permission to use the data can be applied for research purposes via an electronic material request portal. - Proposed research plan must be agreed by the AIRWAVE committee.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Data is only shared with applicants as data users on an approved proposal or amendment.
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Epidemiological terminology - validated questionnaires and examination tools where possible - Standard OMICs terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available

Table A2. STAGE dataset card - ALSPAC

Name of the data	Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children Generation 0 and 1 (ALSPAC)
Date of information	12-06-2024
Study design	Longitudinal birth cohort study
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Bristol, United Kingdom
STAGE partner contact	University of Bristol, Ana Goncalves Soares
Website	https://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/
Link to metadata	https://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/researchers/our-data/
How to apply for data (link)	https://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/researchers/access/
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	University of Bristol
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. ALSPAC data are stored in a dedicated server space at the University of Bristol. Researchers can apply for access to the data which can then be hosted in the researchers own secure data environment.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	ALSPAC data are stored indefinitely (no end date defined).
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	DTA is needed with co-operational organisations needing access to the data. DTA is done once the material request is accepted by the ALSPAC committee.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Ascertained through the data access process.
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ALSPAC datasets are not publicly available. Permission to use the data can be applied for research purposes via an electronic material request portal. - Proposed research plan must be agreed by the ALSPAC committee. Data is to be used solely for teaching and academic research purposes.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	ALSPAC is certified to the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO)/IEC 27001 accreditation for data security. Data is only shared with applicants as data users on an approved proposal or amendment.
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Epidemiological terminology - validated questionnaires and examination tools where possible - Standard OMICs terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available

Table A3. STAGE dataset card - BiB

Name of the data	Born in Bradford (BiB)
Date of information	12-06-2024
Study design	Longitudinal birth cohort study
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Bradford, United Kingdom
STAGE partner contact	University of Bristol, Gemma Clayton
Website	https://borninbradford.nhs.uk/
Link to metadata	https://borninbradford.github.io/datadict/
How to apply for data (link)	https://borninbradford.nhs.uk/research/how-to-access-data/
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	University of Bristol
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. BiB data are stored in a dedicated server space at the University of Bristol. Researchers can apply for access to the data which can then be hosted in the researchers own secure data environment.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	BiB data are stored indefinitely (no end date defined).
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	DTA is needed with co-operational organisations needing access to the data. DTA is done once the material request is accepted by the BiB committee.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Ascertained through the data access process.
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The BiB datasets are not publicly available. Permission to use the data can be applied for research purposes via an electronic material request portal. - Proposed research plan must be agreed by the BiB committee.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Data is only shared with applicants as data users on an approved proposal or amendment.
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Epidemiological terminology - validated questionnaires and examination tools where possible - Standard OMICs terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available

Table A4. STAGE dataset card – CIHNR

Name of the data	Copenhagen Infant Health Nurse Records
Date of information	6-6-2024
Study design	Population based cohort
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Denmark
STAGE partner contact	Region Hovedstaden, Jennifer.lyn.baker@regionh.dk
Website	https://www.frederiksborghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/Sider/Copenhagen-Infant-Health-Nurse-Records-(CIHNR)-cohort.aspx
Link to metadata	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37403322/
How to apply for data (link)	https://www.frederiksborghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/Sider/Copenhagen-Infant-Health-Nurse-Records-(CIHNR)-cohort.aspx
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Region Hovedstaden
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. The full CIHNR data are stored in a dedicated server space at the Center for Clinical Research and Prevention (CKFF).
How long will the data remain available and findable?	Data are stored under a rolling renewal process for as long as they are being used for research. Permissions are granted in 10-year increments.
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Access to all data is contingent upon approval of a research project by the steering committee.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Registration of all users at the CKFF, logged servers and/or two factor identification processes
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	As the data contain personally identifiable information, they cannot be publicly available nor shared per Danish regulations.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes. Due to Danish regulations, there are legal restrictions placed upon the sharing of data outside of Denmark. Due to regulations at the CKFF there are regulations upon sharing of data within Denmark
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data descriptions and codes are available in English and Danish - Epidemiological terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available

Table A5. STAGE dataset card - CPC

Name of the data	Copenhagen Perinatal Cohort (CPC)
Date of information	07-06-2024
Study design	Longitudinal birth cohort study
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Denmark
STAGE partner contact	Region Hovedstaden, lise.geisler.bjerregaard@regionh.dk
Website	www.ckff.dk
Link to metadata	www.frederiksberghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/lifecourse-epidemiology/Sider/default.aspx
How to apply for data (link)	www.frederiksberghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/lifecourse-epidemiology/Sider/default.aspx
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Region Hovedstaden
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. The full CPC data are stored in a dedicated server space at the Center for Clinical Research and Prevention (CKFF). A subset of the data is stored at the National Archives.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	Data are stored under a rolling renewal process for as long as they are being used for research. Permissions are granted in 10-year increments. A subset of the data is stored permanently at the National Archives.
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Access to all data is contingent upon approval of a research project by the steering committee.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Registration of all users at the CKFF, logged servers and/or two factor identification processes
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	As the data contain personally identifiable information, they cannot be publicly available nor shared per Danish regulations.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes. Due to Danish regulations, there are legal restrictions placed upon the sharing of data outside of Denmark. Due to regulations at the CKFF there are regulations upon sharing of data within Denmark
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data descriptions and codes are available in English and Danish - Epidemiological terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available

Table A6. STAGE dataset card - CSHRR

Name of the data	Copenhagen School Health Records Register
Date of information	06-06-2024
Study design	Population based cohort
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Denmark
STAGE partner contact	Region Hovedstaden, Jennifer.lyn.baker@regionh.dk
Website	www.ckff.dk
Link to metadata	www.frederiksberghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/lifecourse-epidemiology/Sider/default.aspx
How to apply for data (link)	www.frederiksberghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/lifecourse-epidemiology/Sider/default.aspx
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Region Hovedstaden
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. The full CSHRR data are stored in a dedicated server space at the Center for Clinical Research and Prevention (CKFF). A subset of the data is stored at the National Archives.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	Data are stored under a rolling renewal process for as long as they are being used for research. Permissions are granted in 20-year increments. A subset of the data is stored permanently at the National Archives.
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Access to all data is contingent upon approval of a research project by the steering committee.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Registration of all users at the CKFF, logged servers and/or two factor identification processes
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	As the data contain personally identifiable information, they cannot be publicly available nor shared per Danish regulations.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes. Due to Danish regulations, there are legal restrictions placed upon the sharing of data outside of Denmark. Due to regulations at the CKFF there are regulations upon sharing of data within Denmark
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data descriptions and codes are available in English and Danish - Epidemiological terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available

Table A7. STAGE dataset card - DanFunD

Name of the data	The Danish study of Functional Disorders
Date of information	6-6-2024
Study design	Population based cohort
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Denmark
STAGE partner contact	Region Hovedstaden, Jennifer.lyn.baker@regionh.dk
Website	https://www.frederiksborghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/bfu/danfund/Sider/default.aspx
Link to metadata	https://www.frederiksborghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/bfu/danfund/Sider/Introduktion-til-DanFunD.aspx https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5333638/
How to apply for data (link)	https://www.frederiksborghospital.dk/ckff/sektioner/sfe/bfu/danfund/Sider/default.aspx
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Region Hovedstaden
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. The full DanFunD data are stored in a dedicated server space at the Center for Clinical Research and Prevention (CKFF).
How long will the data remain available and findable?	Data are stored under a rolling renewal process for as long as they are being used for research. Permissions are granted in 10-year increments.
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Access to all data is contingent upon approval of a research project by the steering committee.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Registration of all users at the CKFF, logged servers and/or two factor identification processes
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	As the data contain personally identifiable information, they cannot be publicly available nor shared per Danish regulations.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes. Due to Danish regulations, there are legal restrictions placed upon the sharing of data outside of Denmark. Due to regulations at the CKFF there are regulations upon sharing of data within Denmark. There may also be additional regulations imposed by the informed consent choices of the participants.
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data descriptions and codes are available in English and Danish - Epidemiological terminology

How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available
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Table A8. STAGE dataset card – Generation R

Name of the data	Generation R Study and Generation R Next (jointly called “Generation R”)
Date of information	09-06-2024
Study design	Longitudinal cohort study
Country (origin/provenance of data)	the Netherlands
STAGE partner contact	EMC, Janine Felix
Website	www.generationr.nl
Link to metadata	Partially in the ECCN catalogue of MOLGENIS (https://data-catalogue.molgenisccloud.org/); an openly available metadata catalogue is under construction.
How to apply for data (link)	Request via email to the project lead, Prof. Vincent Jaddoe, via generationr@erasmusmc.nl
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Data managers of Generation R at Erasmus MC on a daily basis. Final responsibility lies with the principal investigator (PI), Prof. Vincent Jaddoe, as an employee of Erasmus MC.
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data are pseudonymised. The pseudonymisation key is only available to the data managers and study leads. - Logistic data (including e.g. addresses and dates of birth) are kept strictly separate from study data (e.g. measurements), and both systems have different IDs. - Data are only shared with external partners after a second, project-specific pseudonymisation. - Data cleaning, including completeness and plausibility checks are performed during and after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists using standard procedures. - Data are stored on the Erasmus MC network, with automated backups. - Data harmonised for the ECCN are stored in a dedicated server at Erasmus MC for DataSHIELD analyses. - According to the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act, Generation R is formally monitored on a yearly basis, which includes an evaluation of logistic and administrative procedures, informed consent procedures, and data storage and security procedures. Generation R also reports on a yearly basis to the medical ethics committee of Erasmus MC on the study progress. - There is an extensive Data Management Plan, in which all procedures are described in more detail.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	All data are stored for 30 years after the end of the study. This procedure is approved by the medical ethics committee of Erasmus MC, participants are informed about this and give consent for this.

<p>How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?</p>	<p>Generation R has a system of “controlled open access”. Requests for data use are discussed in the Generation R Management Team. Such requests are generally viewed positively. Criteria for evaluation are e.g. overlap with ongoing work, use of biological samples, ethical and data use aspects, logistics and financial/staff contribution. There is a strong preference for collaborative projects and an internal contact person is always appointed. Data are shared with external parties only with management team approval, after signing a DTA (standard format approved by the Erasmus MC legal office) and with project-specific pseudonymisation. Data access is given by the data management team of Erasmus MC. We are currently phasing in a Digital Research Environment.</p>
<p>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</p>	<p>For in-person visits to the department: by sharing ID; for remote access: through links with the external partner institute.</p>
<p>Accessibility</p>	
<p>If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.</p>	<p>Generation R data are not publicly available, as the participants have not consented to this. See description above for access procedure.</p>
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p>The EU GDPR is followed, as well as the Dutch Medical Research (Human Subjects) Act. Sharing of individual participant data is based on their informed consent choices.</p>
<p>Interoperability</p>	
<p>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standard epidemiological terminology - Validated questionnaires and examination tools where possible - Standard OMICs terminology
<p>How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?</p>	<p>Through the Generation R data wiki, available for internal researchers and collaborators. An openly available metadata catalogue is under construction.</p>

Table A9. STAGE dataset card - KORA

Name of the data	KORA study
Date of information	29-05-2024
Study design	Prospective population-based adult cohort
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Germany, Region of Augsburg
STAGE partner contact	Prof. Annette Peters KORA PI Dr. Birgit Linkohr KORA Study Coordinator
Website	https://www.helmholtz-munich.de/en/epi/cohort/kora
Link to metadata	https://helmholtz-muenchen.managed-otrs.com/external/
How to apply for data (link)	https://helmholtz-muenchen.managed-otrs.com/external/
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN DEUTSCHES FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM FUER GESUNDHEIT UND UMWELT GMBH (HMGU)
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. KORA data is stored in a dedicated server space at HMGU.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	No end date defined.
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Project Agreement (PV – similar to a DTA) via KORA-PASST is needed with co-operational organisations needing access to the data (see below).
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Ascertained through the data access process.
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	The KORA datasets are not publicly available but can be accessed upon application through the KORA-PASST use and access hub subject to KORA Board approval (https://helmholtz-muenchen.managed-otrs.com/external/) and must fit the scope of the KORA study in collaborative projects with HMGU.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	KORA data applicants have to accept the KORA Terms and Conditions. The EU GDPR applies. In the use of data, KORA follows the EU GDPR (679/2016) and German data protection law. The use of personal data is based on a cohort participant's written informed consent in their latest follow-up study, which may cause limitations to its use.
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data descriptions and code are available in English and German - Epidemiological terminology - ICD coding of morbidity and mortality outcomes - ATC coding of medication

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validated interview or examination tools where possible - Standard OMICs terminology
<p>How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?</p>	<p>Metadata are openly available.</p>

Table A10. STAGE dataset card – NFBC

Name of the data	Northern Finland Birth Cohorts 1966 & Northern Finland Birth Cohorts 1986
Date of information	03-06-2024
Study design	Longitudinal birth cohort study
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Finland
STAGE partner contact	University of Oulu, Iiro Nerg
Website	https://www.oulu.fi/en/university/faculties-and-units/faculty-medicine/northern-finland-birth-cohorts-and-arctic-biobank
Link to metadata	https://www.oulu.fi/en/university/faculties-and-units/faculty-medicine/northern-finland-birth-cohorts-and-arctic-biobank/northern-finland-birth-cohorts
How to apply for data (link)	https://www.oulu.fi/en/university/faculties-and-units/faculty-medicine/northern-finland-birth-cohorts-and-arctic-biobank/nfbc-aineistopyynto
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	University of Oulu
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data completeness and plausibility checks are performed after data acquisition by trained data managers and scientists. NFBC data are stored in a dedicated server space at University of Oulu. Data harmonised for the ECCN with specific IDs are stored in a dedicated server at University of Oulu for DataSHIELD analyses
How long will the data remain available and findable?	NFBC1966 and NFBC1986 data are stored indefinitely (no end date defined).
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	DTA is needed with co-operational organisations needing access to the data. DTA is done once the material request is accepted by the NFBC research program.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Ascertained through the data access process. Personal University of Oulu (UNIV/UFO) account is needed to access the University of Oulu server.
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	The NFBC datasets are not publicly available. Permission to use the data can be applied for research purposes via an electronic material request portal. Proposed research plan must fit the scope of the NFBC research program. Data is to be used solely for teaching and academic research purposes in collaborative projects with University of Oulu.
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	In the use of data, NFBC follows the EU GDPR (679/2016) and the Finnish Data Protection Act.

	The use of personal data is based on a cohort participant's written informed consent in their latest follow-up study, which may cause limitations to its use.
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data descriptions and codes are available in English and Finnish - Epidemiological terminology - ICD coding of morbidities and mortality - ATC coding of medication - validated questionnaires and examination tools where possible - Standard OMICs terminology
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata are openly available.

Table A11. STAGE dataset card - NINFEA

Name of the data	Nascita e INFanzia: gli Effetti dell'Ambiente G0 & G1
Date of information	03-06-2024
Study design	Birth cohort
Country (origin/provenance of data)	Italy
STAGE partner contact	UNITO (Lorenzo.richiardi@unito.it)
Website	www.progettoninfea.it
Link to metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questionnaire (Italian): https://www.progettoninfea.it/tour - Questionnaire with metadata: https://www.progettoninfea.it/inspectors/forms - the Data Catalogue: https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/catalogue/catalogue/#/
How to apply for data (link)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact Maja Popovic: maja.popovic@unito.it - DAA for DataSHIELD analyses: https://www.progettoninfea.it/attachments/93
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	UNITO team working on the NINFEA cohort
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NINFEA data are stored in a dedicated server space, which access is granted only to the administrator(s) - Pseudonymised data can be downloaded and used by the NINFEA team analysts - Data harmonised for the ECCN with specific IDs are stored in a dedicated server at UNITO for DataSHIELD analyses - The NINFEA team is responsible for harmonising and uploading the data for ECCN
How long will the data remain available and findable?	As long as the ECCN is maintained
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Through MOLGENIS and DataSHIELD
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Through the DAA and the institutional email/credential via DataSHIELD
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	Not applicable
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	There is currently no access limitation through DataSHIELD. For DTA or material transfer agreement (MTA) it should be explored on a case-by-case basis
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standard of the MOLGENIS catalogue used by the ECCN

interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NINFEA questionnaire metadata: HTML, JavaScript, CSS
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation is provided in the MOLGENIS catalogue - Some specific scripts for data cleaning and variable definition based on original data are shared internally to those who have access to original data

Table A12. STAGE dataset card - GECCO

Name of the data	The Geoscience and Health Cohort Consortium
Date of information	10-06-2024
Study design	N/A
Country (origin/provenance of data)	The Netherlands
STAGE partner contact	Jeroen Lakerveld
Website	www.gecco.nl
Link to metadata	www.gecco.nl
How to apply for data (link)	https://www.gecco.nl/exposure-data-1/
Data summary	
Who is responsible for data management?	Jeroen Lakerveld
Describe national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures used for data management?	Data manager/ geographer operationalises data (including storing) and develops metadata sheets. The data are environmental exposure variables based on various sources.
How long will the data remain available and findable?	Unspecified
How is access to the data provided, both during and after the end of the project?	Unknown, but likely for at least 10 years
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Data request procedure
Accessibility	
If certain datasets cannot be shared (or are shared under restricted access conditions), explain why. Separate legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.	Not Applicable
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Not Applicable
Interoperability	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies are followed to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?	Not Applicable
How do you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?	Metadata sheets include documentation

ANNEX 2 – ADMINISTRATIVE HEALTH DATA & BIOBANKS

There are three “non-cohort” datasets that will be utilised in STAGE research activities. Due to the nature of these data sources, there is no data controller for these data in STAGE. In Table B1 are listed the websites of these data sources, where documentation and other information can be found. Also, a contact person within STAGE is listed.

Table B1. Administrative health data & biobanks

Data	Website	STAGE contact
FinnGen	www.finngen.fi/en	Iiro Nerg, UOULU
Health Search	www.healthsearch.it	Andrea Piano Mortari, UTOURV
UK Biobank	www.ukbiobank.ac.uk	Gemma Clayton, UOB